

White Paper ID Number W035

Title of White Paper Mid- Through Far-Infrared Astronomy: The Path to Tomorrow

ID of Associated Expression of Interest E026

Topic Area of White Paper

science programs, science topics and science themes

Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

The mid- through far-infrared wavelength regime accounts for the second largest component of the spectral energy distribution of the Universe – below the primordial cosmic background and similar in magnitude to the optical background. The far-infrared peak is due to prolific star formation within galaxies during the early lifetime of the Universe, with the stellar emission obscured by enshrouding dust and re-emitted at longer (as well as red-shifted) wavelengths. Despite their importance for the energy budget of the Universe, these infrared wavelengths remain among the least investigated, primarily due to the difficulty in launching appropriate instruments.

Beyond the clear importance of the mid- through far-infrared continuum as an indicator of how, where, and when the galaxies in the Universe emit energy, this wavelength regime is also abundant in spectroscopic diagnostics, including those from light molecules such as H₂ and HD, important for direct determinations of gas mass (independent of metallicity and freeze-out). This is also the most important part of the electromagnetic spectrum for observations of water, in both gas and ice form, and thus a key probe into the pathway to life around stars. Furthermore, a wealth of fine-structure lines probes the ionized regions around hot stars and active galactic nuclei – providing essential diagnostics of temperature, metallicity, and hardness of the radiation field. Similarly, dust features manifest strongly in this window, including emission from PAHs, silicates, minerals, and both crystalline and amorphous ices. When combined with the fine-structure lines, PAH and dust emission provide important diagnostics for the energy budget of galaxies.

Many of the specific science questions posed by mid- through far-infrared observations, and discussed in this white paper, directly relate to how the Universe, our Galaxy, our Sun, our Solar System, and the Earth began and have evolved up to this point in time (indeed that is why the NASA-concept is named the Origins Space Telescope). In order to provide answers to these questions, the above studies necessarily bring together the entire "astro-turf", including astronomy, astrophysics, astrochemistry, and astrobiology.

The next generation of mid- through far-infrared space telescopes are already in the planning stage (i.e. SPICA and Origins). While these telescopes will not improve significantly the angular resolution over previous missions, they are both designed to be extremely sensitive, beating Herschel by two to three orders of magnitude. The science cases utilizing such observational opportunities discussed in this white paper show both the importance of these wavelengths for a broad range of research and the leadership roles of Canadian astronomers in these fields. It is also important to note that, as was the case with previous mid- through far-infrared missions, this extreme increase in telescope capability will almost certainly lead to significant 'discovery science', unanticipated at present.

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1 Mid- Through Far-Infrared Astronomy: The Path to Tomorrow

The mid- through far-infrared wavelength range (roughly 5–250 μm) has been accessible to astronomers for less than forty years, since the launch of the Infrared Astronomical Satellite (*IRAS*), with a 57 cm mirror, in 1983. Already with that first effort astronomers realized the key insights that this wavelength window enabled, from dusty debris disks around stars, through dense star-forming cores, to starburst galaxies at high redshift. The novel results from *IRAS* led, a decade later, to the launch of the Infrared Space Observatory (*ISO*) with a 60 cm mirror and improved instrumentation allowing for the discovery of water vapour across many astronomical environments, including the atmospheres of planets in our Solar System, identification of crystalline features in dusty objects, and an unveiling of a cold (~ 20 K) dust component within Galaxies. Spectroscopy further provided measurement of the strength of important cooling lines from atoms, ions, and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), and allowed the use of these lines' ratios as diagnostics of the underlying physical conditions in the interstellar medium.

The overwhelming scientific success of *IRAS* and *ISO* supported the next generation of larger and more sensitive telescopes dedicated to infrared astronomy – the Spitzer Space Telescope (*Spitzer*, 85 cm mirror) launched in 2003, focusing on the near- to mid-infrared while the Herschel Space Observatory (*Herschel*, 3.3 m mirror) launched in 2009, observing the far-infrared. Both of these space-based platforms for infrared astronomy combined guaranteed-time and dedicated key projects with open-time proposals from the astronomical community, and were extremely proficient in opening the infrared to *all* astronomers. Canadian researchers were significantly involved with both telescopes. With *Herschel*, Canada leveraged its direct involvement in two of the science instruments to allow Canadians into leadership roles in key investigations including galaxy evolution, star-forming regions, the water trail to life, and debris disks. According to independent analysis for the Canadian Space Agency (CSA), *Herschel* has provided the highest publication return from any of the CSA's supported missions (Laurin et al. 2019, CASCA Annual General Meeting).

The imminent launch of *JWST*, with a 6.5 m mirror, promises significantly higher resolution and sensitivity beyond *Spitzer* and Canadian astronomers are poised to play leadership roles through both open time and guaranteed time observing (see white paper E038 by Doyon et al.). At present, however, there are only proposed space-based missions reaching to the far-infrared wavelength range of *Herschel*. *SPICA* (2.5 m, 12 - 350 μm), a joint European/Japanese mission concept, is undergoing review by the European Space Agency and is discussed in a separate white paper (E001 by Naylor et al.). In the U.S., the possibility of an *Origins Space Telescope (Origins)* (5.9 m, 2.5 - 588 μm) has been investigated, costed-out, and submitted to the US Decadal Survey (available at asd.gsfc.nasa.gov/firs/). Both of these mission proposals include mid- and far-infrared instrumentation.

Over the 36 years since the launch of *IRAS*, we have learned that the mid- through far-infrared is an extremely rich and exciting part of the electromagnetic spectrum. Dust, which obscures much of the Universe, typically equilibrates at temperatures between 10 and 100 K, peaking in thermal emission within this window. Furthermore, spectroscopic diagnostic features are abundant and trace gas-phase molecules, atoms, and ions, as well as solid-state features from ices and minerals. Given this extreme richness, it is reasonable to question why there have been only a handful of instruments, with limited lifetimes, dedicated to these wavelengths.

The complications begin with the Earth's atmosphere, which is opaque to most of the mid- through far-infrared window. Thus, space-based missions are required for the best and broadest observing opportunities, and telescope size and mass are harshly constrained. Balloon-borne missions, e.g. BLAST, also play an important role in opening this window (see E073 by Fissel et al.); however, their significantly limited flight times and payloads yield only specialized access and investigations. Similarly, high-altitude plane-based mid- through far-infrared telescopes, such as SOFIA, provide enhanced instrument platforms but still suffer significantly from both the atmosphere and warm telescope optics. The equilibrium temperature of a shielded telescope, even in Earth's orbit, remains above 80 K unless actively cooled. At these temperatures, the thermal emission from the telescope dominates over most astronomical sources. Even without actively cooling the mirror, the instrumentation requires cryogenic temperatures to function, necessitating some cooling on board space-based missions. In the past, expendable liquid helium has been used as an in-orbit coolant, increasing launch mass (and therefore cost) and limiting the telescope lifetime. Future missions, such as *SPICA* and *Origins*, plan to use mechanical cryocoolers and passive radiators to keep even the telescope mirror below 10 K and extend their lifetimes. Thus, the next generation of space-based

Figure 1: Observed spectral energy distribution of the Universe, from a compilation of data over all frequencies (Hill, Masui, & Scott 2018, *Applied Spectroscopy*, 72, 663). Note the height of the mid- to far-infrared peak in relation to both the cosmic background radiation and the optical emission from evolved galaxies. The cosmic infrared background (CIB, from dust-reprocessed starlight) has approximately the same total energy density as the cosmic optical background (COB, from direct starlight).

mid- through far-infrared telescopes should be able to achieve sensitivities $100\times$ (e.g. *SPICA*) or potentially $1000\times$ (e.g. *Origins*) times better than *Herschel* and the possibility of lifetimes longer than five years.

A second complication of space-based mid- through far-infrared astronomy is still to be overcome, however. It remains extremely difficult (and expensive) to design, build, and launch large-aperture telescopes. Given that the angular resolution obtained depends on the ratio of the photon size to mirror size, until space-based interferometry is enabled, infrared astronomers will have to deal with relatively poor angular resolution. Quantifying this, *Herschel*, with a 3.5-m mirror, had an angular resolution of $7''$ at $100\ \mu\text{m}$, while *SPICA*'s 2.5-m mirror offers $10''$ and the *Origins* 5.9-m mirror achieves $\sim 4''$. Optical telescopes and (sub)millimeter and radio interferometers can achieve $< 0.1''$ angular resolutions, which can only be matched at far-infrared wavelengths using space-based interferometry with \sim kilometer baselines (e.g. *FIRI*: Helmich & Ivison, 2009, *Experimental Astronomy*, 23, 235).

Despite their moderate angular resolution, the enhanced sensitivities of both *SPICA* and *Origins* offer an exceptional advance in mid- through far-infrared astronomical research and both missions have designed their instrumentation to make the best use of the observatory conditions (E001; Roelfsema et al. 2018, *PASA*, 35, 30; asd.gsfc.nasa.gov/firs/). Thus, both telescopes have: (1) far-infrared broad-band spectrometers to simultaneously measure diagnostic ion, atom, molecule, and solid state features in individual astronomical sources; (2) mid-infrared cameras with spectroscopic modes for 3-D mapping; and (3) far-infrared polarimetric imagers dedicated to unravelling the importance of magnetic fields in the interstellar medium. In the following pages, we detail the exciting science that either of these next generation mid- through far-infrared space telescopes will enable and explain the importance to Canada of participating in these missions. Where appropriate, we also note the necessity of achieving higher angular resolution observations, and thus the need for continued development of space-based interferometry.

2 The Importance of Mid- Through Far-Infrared Astronomy

The mid- through far-infrared wavelength regime accounts for the second largest component of the spectral energy distribution of the Universe – below the primordial cosmic background and similar in magnitude to the optical background (Fig. 1). The far-infrared peak is due to prolific star formation within galaxies during the early lifetime of the Universe, with the stellar emission obscured by enshrouding dust and re-emitted at longer (as well as redshifted) wavelengths. Despite their importance for the energy budget of the Universe, these infrared wavelengths remain among the least investigated, primarily due to the difficulty in launching appropriate instruments (see §1).

Beyond the clear importance of the mid- through far-infrared continuum as an indicator of how, where, and when the galaxies in the Universe emit energy, this wavelength regime is also abundant in spectroscopic diagnostics, including those from light molecules such as H_2 and HD, important for direct determinations of gas mass (independent of metallicity and freeze-out). This is also the most important part of the electromagnetic spectrum

Figure 2: *Top*: Key infrared ionic fine-structure lines as a function of infrared wavelength and ionization potential. Note the wide range of rest frame mid- through far-infrared wavelengths. *Bottom*: Molecular and solid-state features visible in the mid- through far-infrared. Note the large number of transitions available for critical molecules such as H_2 , HD, CO, OH, and water. Figure taken from the SPICA-ESA M5 Proposal.

for observations of water, in both gas and ice form, and thus a key probe into the pathway to life around stars. Furthermore, a wealth of fine-structure lines probes the ionized regions around hot stars and active galactic nuclei – providing essential diagnostics of temperature, metallicity, and hardness of the radiation field. Similarly, dust features manifest strongly in this window, including emission from PAHs, silicates, minerals, and both crystalline and amorphous ices. When combined with the fine-structure lines, PAH and dust emission provide important diagnostics for the energy budget of galaxies. Figure 2 presents a visual indication of this wealth of spectroscopic diagnostics (see also the Molecular Astrophysics and Astrochemistry white paper E063 by Cami et al.).

For observations of star-forming regions within our own Galaxy, *Herschel* already had sufficient sensitivity to uncover the bulk of the continuum emission at mid- through far-infrared wavelengths. Nevertheless, the extreme increase in continuum sensitivity available from next generation missions (*SPICA* and *Origins*), coupled with the exquisite stability of space, is essential for polarimetric labelling of photons and thus a determination of the morphology, topology, and physical importance of magnetic fields during the star-formation process. Additionally, beginning with the epoch of *Herschel*, investigations into time evolution of protostellar brightness have shown promise as an effective probe of stellar-mass-assembly and circumstellar-disk physics. Combining the increased raw sensitivity of the next generation missions with enhanced calibration precision will enable effective time domain studies, in synergy with the push into time domain across all of astronomy.

For all of the above reasons, it is clear that investigations at mid- through far-infrared wavelengths are important for astrophysics, astrochemistry, and even astrobiology. In the next five sections we discuss in order the specific science cases targeting: galaxy evolution; the baryonic cycle within galaxies; star-formation in molecular clouds; the evolution of (proto)planetary disks; and the atmospheres of exoplanets.

3 Galaxy Evolution Across Cosmic Time

The “cosmic noon” period ($z \simeq 1-3$) saw star-formation and black-hole-assembly rates (the two processes appear to be interlinked) that were an order of magnitude higher than today (see Madau & Dickinson 2014, ARAA, 52, 415 for a review). The bulk of this intense activity took place behind a thick veil of obscuring dust. As such, traditional rest-frame UV and optical diagnostics are diminished and extinguished, whereas numerous diagnostic infrared fine-structure lines provide a direct determination of the energetic processes at play inside these dust-enshrouded galaxies. By increasing the raw sensitivity to infrared emission over *Herschel* by a factor between 100 (*SPICA*) and 1000 (*Origins*), the next generation of mid- through far-infrared space telescopes will be extremely powerful for investigating the process of galaxy evolution across all relevant epochs through measurement of spectroscopic diagnostic lines (Fig. 2, Top Panel).

Mid- through far-infrared observations of galaxies offer the ability to trace the co-evolution of the stellar component of galaxies and their central black holes through determination of the energy budget and hardness of the

radiation field within each galaxy (e.g. US Decadal White Paper [DWP] by Pope et al. 2019, BAAS, 51, 330). The key is to identify lines and line ratios that probe the energetics from hot stars, supernovae, stellar winds, and AGN. Furthermore, these same lines provide a direct determination of the metallicity (e.g. oxygen, nitrogen, neon, and sulphur) and therefore of galaxy assembly pathways and of the efficiency of gas cooling within the interstellar medium (e.g. DWP by Smith et al. 2019, BAAS, 51, 400).

Statistically-significant samples that span a range of luminosity and environment are key. These will let us go beyond the bulk characterization of the cosmic star-formation and black-hole-growth history to study how the assembly of dust-enshrouded galaxies and black holes is governed by both intrinsic and environmental processes. To achieve this goal, thousands of galaxies out to redshifts 4–6 will need to be observed using broad-band low- and medium-resolution spectroscopy, and hence survey speed is vital. With this in mind, space telescopes of the next generation have developed powerful wavelength-multiplexing far-infrared spectrometers targeting individual locations on the sky. For both *SPICA* and *Origins*, Canadian Fourier Transform Spectroscopy technology, led by David Naylor at Lethbridge, is essential for these instruments to succeed (see also E001).

Along with the dedicated far-infrared survey of individual galaxies, these next generation space telescopes will perform blind spatial/spectral surveys on many square-degree scales and over all redshifts at mid-infrared wavelengths. Primarily detecting red-shifted PAH emission, of order 10^5 sources (galaxies and AGN) will be uncovered. Most of these will be at moderate redshift ($z = 0.5-1$) although hundreds of $z > 4$ objects will also be revealed. These samples will provide an unbiased census of cosmic star formation across a range of environments.

The spatial resolution of *Herschel* was only sufficient to separate into individual galaxies about half the extragalactic far-infrared continuum emission (even less at shorter wavelengths). Thus, significant gains in direct continuum imaging of galaxies across cosmic time will only occur when significantly larger apertures or space-based interferometry become available. Nevertheless, the next generation of sensitive spectrometers investigating the spectral dimension of galaxies will allow for separation of sources in redshift space, even within a single telescope beam.

Canadians used Spitzer for studies of stellar populations and star formation indicators in nearby galaxies (Rafiei Ravandi et al. 2016, MNRAS, 459, 1403 ; Rahmani et al. 2016, MNRAS, 456, 4128; Lenkic et al. 2016, MNRAS, 459, 2948) as well as for understanding the structure of quasar accretion discs through their mid-infrared spectra (Hill et al. 2014, MNRAS, 438, 2317). Canadians also played leading roles in studies of galaxy evolution using continuum measurements from the BLAST balloon experiment and the SPIRE instrument on *Herschel*, as well as with SCUBA and SCUBA-2 on the JCMT. Research in this area has produced around 20 PhD theses including a CASCA Plaskett award-winning dissertation using SCUBA by Tracy Webb (2003) and two UBC theses based on *Spitzer* measurements (Pope & Sajina). *SPICA* and *Origins* will enable spectroscopic studies of the same kinds of high- z star-forming galaxies that have previously only been studied in continuum emission at these wavelengths. Leveraging our previous success, Canadians, have been directly involved from the beginning in developing the extragalactic science case for both mission concepts.

4 The Baryonic Cycle in Nearby Galaxies

For nearby galaxies the next generation of mid- through far-infrared space telescopes will allow astronomers to spatially probe the baryon cycle in galaxies, investigating how matter moves between being in a predominantly gaseous state within the interstellar medium and being bound up in stars (Fig. 3). This baryon cycle is an important area of Canadian research and a detailed discussion of the many physical processes at play within is provided in a separate white paper (E024 by Rosolowsky et al.).

Utilizing the same suite of atomic and ionic fine-structure lines discussed earlier (Fig. 2) the origin and observed spread in star-formation rates within and across galaxies will be explored with high sensitivity. There is now strong evidence that the specific rate of star formation (the star-formation rate per unit stellar mass) varies significantly between normal galaxies and starbursts, and that galactic morphology, metallicity, and environment play a role. However, many of the details are still poorly understood, including the relative roles of local versus global processes in determining the star-formation rate, the physical processes that affect the evolution of dust within galaxies, and

Figure 3: Schematic diagram showing the various interactions underlying the processing of baryonic material within galaxies. Note the multiple routes and strongly varying environments partaking in the galactic ecosystem. Figure from the Origins Space Telescope submission to the US Decadal Report.

the importance of internal and external reservoirs of matter in determining the star-formation history (DWP by Bolatto et al. 2019, BAAS, 51, 71; van der Tak et al. 2018, PASA, 53, 2).

Nearby galaxies can be spatially resolved in the mid- through far-infrared, even at the modest resolutions available with the next generation of space telescopes. For example, *SPICA* at $100\ \mu\text{m}$ will provide 2-pc resolution in the Magellanic Clouds. The key improvement, however, will be the much higher sensitivity available, allowing efficient spectroscopic mapping of nearby galaxies, including the bright and active star-forming regions, sites of supernovae, fainter quiescent regions, and central nuclear activity (see Fig. 3). Through mapping it will be possible to separate and calibrate diagnostic lines, for example the key star-formation indicator [CII] ($157\ \mu\text{m}$), and important line ratios, by galactic environment. This undertaking is a necessary first step to applying these line diagnostics comprehensively, and as a full suite, toward more distant sources (§3) where star-forming regions and AGN are convolved together.

For determining baryonic content, the HD lines (56 and $112\ \mu\text{m}$) provide a direct measure of the gas mass in molecular clouds within galaxies. These far-infrared diagnostics allow one to bypass the complicated scaling relations required when measuring only CO, which is dependent on both metallicity and the relative importance of CO-dark gas. Indeed, by combining HD observations with ground-based CO measurements it will be possible to calibrate the importance of CO-dark gas as a function of environment within individual nearby galaxies.

Precise determination of the emissivity properties of dust in nearby galaxies as a function of type and environment is an essential step in determining the dust mass and its evolution over cosmic time within more distant galaxies. Such measurements require both broad spectral coverage across the mid- through far-infrared and a detailed understanding of the observed environment (see also E076 by Sadavoy et al.; DWP by Sadavoy et al. 2019, BAAS, 51, 66). These spatially resolved maps of nearby galaxies will also allow for a quantification of the main formation mechanisms of dust (e.g., AGB stars versus supernovae, see DWP by Matsuura et al. 2019). Time-dependent monitoring of at least a handful of supernovae in nearby galaxies (where the spatial resolution is sufficient to localize the effects of dust formation) is a distinct possibility. Furthermore, the ability to measure features within crystalline silicates will allow for determination of the main physical processing mechanisms of dust, such as cosmic ray amorphitization.

The Canadian community has played leading roles in studying the baryon cycling within galaxies, notably through CO studies with the JCMT (the NGLS and JINGLE Legacy surveys) and ALMA (PHANGS and VERTICO Large Programs). Using the unbiased HD tracer to survey molecular gas will secure the legacy of this work and open new insights in low metallicity systems. There have been many Canadian PhDs on nearby galaxies in the last ten years alone, including at Manitoba (West), McMaster (Parkin, Mok, Schirm), and Toronto (Rivera-Ingraham). Canadian researchers have also developed a physical motivated understanding of the variations in PAH features from *Spitzer* spectroscopy that will allow these tracers to be used as spectroscopic diagnostics of feedback and radiation field (Stock & Peeters, 2017, ApJ, 837 129).

Figure 4: *Planck* determination (using a “drapery” algorithm) of the magnetic field topology around Taurus, at $3'$ to $5'$ scales, superposed on *Herschel* observations of thin filaments at $10''$ scales. Note how in this location the magnetic field orientation is roughly perpendicular to the main filament. Figure from the SPICA submission to the US Decadal Report.

5 Star Formation in Galactic Molecular Clouds

The study and understanding of star formation within our own galaxy has been strongly influenced by observations in the mid- through far-infrared. A key *Herschel* result is the ubiquity and importance of filamentary structures within molecular clouds (André, Di Francesco, et al. 2014, PPVI, 27), and their connection to the formation of individual stars and stellar groups. It is now understood that competition between magnetic support and gravitational collapse within clouds, mediated by supersonic turbulent-like motions which both supports and compresses the molecular gas, is an essential component in the determination of the star-formation rate. Canadians remain key players in this area of investigation. Indeed, a number of Canadian PhD theses on this topic have led to research positions at Canadian institutions (e.g. Fissel, Friesen, Kirk, Sadavoy). A detailed discussion of star formation in molecular clouds is provided in a separate white paper (E025 by Di Francesco et al.).

Despite this general understanding of the main ingredients responsible for setting and regulating star formation within molecular clouds, there are still too many specific measurements lacking to allow for a quantifiable theory describing the star-formation rate as a function of environment and determining the resultant distribution of stellar masses (i.e., the stellar initial-mass function). In particular, two key measurements of the physical conditions within molecular clouds remain poorly explored: determination of the energy dissipation rate due to shocks and shears within the turbulent gas; and a measurement of the importance of magnetic fields. Both of these properties are accessible with mid- through far-infrared observations (André et al. 2019, PASA, 36, 29; van der Tak et al. 2018, PASA, 53, 2).

Individual molecular clouds provide a snapshot detailing the kinematics and (column) density distribution at a single point in time. Comparison with evolutionary theoretical models is severely hampered by our inability to determine the rate at which the molecular cloud gains or loses energy over time. To estimate the rate of energy dissipated in molecular clouds requires measurement of the line emission responsible for cooling the shock-heated gas. Direct tracers include mid- through high- J CO lines and [OI] at 63 and $145 \mu\text{m}$, as well as H_2 in regions of low density. First attempts at estimating the importance of energy dissipation were under-taken in Canada, at CITA, prior to the launch of *Herschel* (Basu & Murali 2001, ApJ, 551, 743) and guaranteed time observations with *Herschel* were used by a Canadian PhD student as part of his CASCA Plaskett award-winning dissertation (Pon 2013, PhD Thesis, University of Victoria). While the limited sensitivity of *Herschel* allowed only proof-of-concept results, the significantly enhanced ($100 - 1000\times$) next generation of mid- through far- infrared space telescopes will be capable of mapping entire clouds in these important diagnostic lines, thus quantifying not only the energy dissipation rate but also correlating the dissipation with observable structure, i.e. filaments and velocity shears.

Determining the role of magnetic fields in the support and evolution of molecular clouds has also proved extremely difficult to date (DWP by Fissel et al. 2019; André et al. 2019, PASA, 36, 29). Within molecular clouds, non-spherical grains align their minor axis with the local direction of the magnetic field, thus producing a small but measurable (few percent) polarization fraction in continuum emission, which can be used to infer the magnetic field morphology and topology. Ground-based measurements of continuum polarization at millimetre and submillimetre wavelengths have been attempted for over 25 years, with Canadians playing leadership roles in both

the instrument building and the investigation planning. Many of the most important ground-based instruments have led to Canadian PhD dissertations, including SCUPOL (Matthews, McMaster), BLASTPol (Fissel, University of Toronto), and POL2 (Coudé, University of Montreal). Such measurements, however, remain significantly hampered by the lack of atmospheric stability and complications achieving the required degree of calibration.

Space-based observations of dust continuum polarization with the next generation of mid- through far-infrared space telescopes will be game-changing in this regard. *Planck* has demonstrated the power of polarimetric measurements from space, providing amazing images of the magnetic field topology across the Galaxy (Fig. 4), despite having poor spatial resolution ($3'$ to $5'$), and provided roadmaps to the science that can be uncovered – including constraining dust alignment physics and dust evolution. The exquisite continuum sensitivity of the next generation of space telescopes will allow for high signal to noise polarimetric images of even the fainter parts of molecular clouds with ~ 60 times better angular resolution than *Planck* – essentially the continuum capability of *Herschel* for studying molecular clouds will become the polarimetric capability of the next space telescopes! Thus, where *Herschel* uncovered the importance of filaments and their association with prestellar and protostellar cores, the morphology and topology of the underlying magnetic field from the scale of cores and filaments to the entire cloud will be revealed. And, as importantly, comparison between the magnetic-field geometry and the measured kinematics of the molecular gas provides estimates of the underlying magnetic-field strength.

Additional key parameters in our understanding of the structure and evolution of interstellar clouds, star-forming regions, and protoplanetary disks are heating and cooling rates. For these environments, PAHs provide the dominant source of heating through the photo-electric effect. As these species are abundantly present and pervade the Universe, their diagnostic power of the physical conditions and the star formation rate is invaluable across research disciplines (§3, 4, and 6), in spite of big gaps in our knowledge and understanding of the details of the underlying PAH population. Canadian researchers are at the forefront of state-of-the-art studies on the formation, evolution and destruction of PAHs and their cousins, fullerenes – species that were discovered by Canadian researchers. While *Spitzer* efforts concentrated on probing the photo-chemical evolution of these species, driven by the physical conditions of the host environment, progress was hampered by the lack of spatial resolution. A *JWST*-ERS program (with a large Canadian involvement) will resolve and directly observe, for the first time, the response of PDR gas to the penetrating far-ultraviolet photon flux in key zones: i.e. the ionization front and the HI/H₂ photo dissociation front, at unprecedented spectral and spatial detail over the full mid-infrared wavelength range. This will allow us to quantify the response of these species to the detailed physical conditions and lead to a comprehensive view of how these molecules affect their environment and the other way around. Such information will be invaluable for high-*z* studies of galaxies with *SPICA* and *Origins*.

One additional area of Galactic star-formation research that has been pioneered in Canada is time-domain monitoring of the brightness of deeply embedded protostars as a proxy for mass assembly, given that the luminosity of protostars is dominated by accretion, and as a probe into the (unstable) dynamics within the mass-feeding protoplanetary disk (DWP) by Fischer et al. 2019, BAAS, 51, 495; Green et al. 2019, BAAS, 51, 372). Ground-based efforts have concentrated on submillimetre continuum emission, which responds directly to the temperature changes in the envelope due to heating and have revealed that low-amplitude protostellar variability is common and observable over several years (Mairs et al 2017, ApJ, 849, 107; Johnstone et al. 2018, ApJ, 854, 31). The strength of the variability should be significantly stronger in the mid- through far-infrared, closer to the peak of the dusty envelope emission; hence multi-year monitoring from space will allow for significant scientific return.

6 Evolution of Protoplanetary Disks

Ground-based submillimetre interferometry and near-infrared extreme adaptive optics have revolutionized our understanding of the structure and evolution of disks around young stars, especially in connection with planet formation. Canada is extremely active in this research area and much detail is presented in a separate white paper (E013 by van der Marel).

Mid- through far-infrared wavelengths have an essential role to play in our understanding of the evolution of protoplanetary disks, but until the era of space-based interferometers, we will not have the ability to spatially

Figure 5: Cartoon showing the expected spectral energy of a protoplanetary disk system observed in the mid- through far-infrared. Also noted are the locations in the disk where the key spectral features emit. Figure adapted from the SPICA-ESA M5 Proposal. .

resolve structure. The next generation of single-dish space telescopes, however, offer a complementary approach to the exquisite high-resolution imaging in the near-infrared and submillimetre bands by kinematically resolving disk features using important gas tracers such as HD, H₂, CO, and water lines (DWP by Oberg et al. 2019, BAAS, 51, 165). Through large statistical surveys of 100s to 1000s of forming stars, the evolution of protoplanetary disks will be unveiled (see Fig. 5). For example, HD can be used to directly determine the gas content, independent of freeze-out calibration factors, while low- through high- J CO lines will probe the surface layer of the disk, and fine-structure lines will be used to measure the rate of gas dispersal/photoevaporation of the disk. Finally, water will be observed in both gaseous and solid ice form, in order to deduce the manner in which it gets locked up in planets, as a necessary ingredient for life as we know it (DWPs by Bergin et al. 2019, BAAS, 51, 222; Lis et al. 2019, BAAS, 51, 111). From the water spectrum, the location in the disk where water freezes out (the snow line) can be deduced and compared with the snow lines of other species observed with ALMA.

Broad-band mineralogy across the phases of star formation, from young accretion disks through old debris disks, will additionally provide a unique indication of the processing of dust within disks and add additional insight into planet formation (see DWPs by Su et al. 2019, BAAS, 51, 419; Chen et al. 2019, BAAS, 51, 342).

Canadians played an out-sized role in *Herschel* observations of debris disks, including leading the open-time large program DEBRIS (Matthews et al. 2010, A&A, 518, 135) which resulted in key observations of HR 8799, τ Ceti, AU Mic (Matthews et al. ApJ, 780, 97; Lawler et al. 2014, MNRAS, 444, 2665; Matthews et al. ApJ, 811, 100). The next generation of mid- through far-infrared space telescopes, with their significant increase in sensitivity and hence mapping speed will be extremely efficient at uncovering new debris disks.

7 Exoplanet Atmospheres

Having a significantly enhanced sensitivity and stability, the next generation of space telescopes can be used to monitor the atmospheres of exoplanets, pushing well past the limits of *JWST*. The *Origins* mission intends to have a mid-infrared instrument specifically designed for monitoring exoplanet atmospheres, via both transmission and emission spectroscopy. Habitability signatures, such as CO₂ and water, along with the first detections of biosignatures, such as N₂O, CH₄, and ozone, will be observed in the atmospheres of terrestrial planets orbiting M and K stars in order to determine if these planets can sustain life. Furthermore, the degree of cloudiness will be revealed and, with long-term monitoring, both intermittent weather effects and seasonal variations in temperature will be observed to determine the likelihood of liquid water on the planet's surface (see DWPs by Kataria et al. 2019; Line et al. 2019, BAAS, 51, 271).

The search for, and characterization of, exoplanets has been an important Canadian pursuit since the the 1980's and continues to grow in importance, see for example PhD dissertations by Marois and Lafrenière. Furthermore, Canadian leadership on the NIRISS instrument for *JWST* has resulted in the significant growth of a research community dedicated to the analysis of exoplanet atmospheric spectra.

8 Final Thoughts/Recommendations

The next generation of mid- through far-infrared space telescopes are already in the planning stage (i.e. *SPICA* and *Origins*). While these telescopes will not improve significantly the angular resolution over previous missions, they are both designed to be extremely sensitive, beating *Herschel* by two to three orders of magnitude. The science cases utilizing such observational opportunities discussed in this white paper show both the importance of these wavelengths for a broad range of research and the leadership roles of Canadian astronomers in these fields. It is also important to note that, as was the case with previous mid- through far-infrared missions, this extreme increase in telescope capability will almost certainly lead to significant ‘discovery science’, unanticipated at present.

It is essential that the Long Range Plan 2020 supports our investment in at least one of these space-based missions in order to leverage Canada’s accumulated knowledge and leadership. We have an excellent and timely opportunity to participate in these international projects from their inception and thus play an out-sized role in making the missions successful scientifically. Such an opportunity, however, necessitates cradle-to-grave funding, allowing Canadians to work on the science competitively, before, during, and after flight.

Research support for Canadian astronomers invested in large international space missions is critical. In order to fully leverage Canadian investments in hardware and for Canadian astronomers to be competitive with our colleagues around the globe, support for scientific exploration and publication of the obtained data is required (as for example provided by NASA to US astronomers). We therefore applaud the recent announcement from the CSA to support *JWST* science by providing funding to GTO programs at a level of 2.5K/hr. We strongly recommend similar funding for *JWST* ERS and GO programs as well as future space missions.

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

Mid- through far-infrared wavelengths provide the second largest component of the spectral energy distribution of the Universe (§2). Spectroscopic diagnostic features are abundant and trace gas-phase molecules, atoms, and ions, as well as solid-state features from ices and minerals. An additional advantage of these diagnostics is that they are only weakly affected by dust extinction. Furthermore, polarimetric measurements of dust offers an opportunity to determine the strength and importance of magnetic fields in the interstellar medium.

These wavelengths have only been explored by a handful of space-based missions to date. The next generation of missions are expected to be at least two orders of magnitude more sensitive and will thus undoubtedly open up new and unexplored areas of research, along with the key known science discussed in this white paper.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

Maintaining a critical mass of astronomers in Canada utilizing the mid- through far-infrared is essential if we are to be world leaders in this science. The best way to ensure that this happens is to be involved, from the start, in the next generation of missions – as we have done with both *SPICA* and *Origins*.

Continued access to the submillimetre, through interferometry (*ALMA*) and single-dish survey telescopes (*JCMT* and/or *CCAT-p*) provides long-wavelength support for many of these research areas. Furthermore, near- through mid-infrared space-based observations will be supplied by *JWST* through the next decade. The missing link in this mix of telescopes is access to the mid- through far-infrared window.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

Canadian leadership is already in place within *SPICA*, with David Naylor bringing essential Fourier Transform Spectrometer technical knowledge to the project (E001). As well, the Canadian researchers that played central

roles in *Herschel* key projects are available and ready to take on leadership roles once Canada joins a funded mission. Canadians (Douglas Scott and Doug Johnstone) were part of the science and technology study group for *Origins* (see asd.gsfc.nasa.gov/firs/) and several Canadians have been involved with writing the published science cases for *SPICA* (see spica-mission.org).

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

There is significant synergy with Canadian users of the JCMT and ALMA, with well-established communities in both Galactic and extragalactic studies. For many of these research areas, a very strong scientific connection will develop with *JWST* and the SKA.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

These planned space missions are not expected to launch until beyond 2030. Nevertheless, the technical design and scientific planning will be well under way for either mission by the middle of the 2020s.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

Space programs are expensive and Canada is typically a small partner. However, experience from *Herschel* shows that Canadian researchers are well prepared to play an out-sized role in the scientific return of the next mid- through far-infrared space-based mission (see §1).

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

The risks for *SPICA* are described in the white paper specifically devoted to that mission.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

For the technical aspects of *SPICA*, see its white paper (E001). Similar results will apply for any mid- through far-infrared space mission. For the scientific case presented here, the broad-range of research opportunities at these wavelengths are well adapted to graduate student theses, postdoctoral investigations, and undergraduate projects, as was the case with *Herschel*.

Many of the specific science questions posed by mid- through far-infrared observations directly relate to how the Universe, our Galaxy, our Sun, our Solar System, and the Earth began and have evolved up to this point in time (indeed that is why the NASA-concept is named the *Origins Space Telescope*). In order to provide answers to these questions, the above studies necessarily bring together the entire *astro-turf*, including astronomy, astrophysics, astrochemistry, and astrobiology.

The fields of study discussed here directly relate to some of the deepest questions that the general public regard as important and worthy of astronomy research. As such, these areas of research provide an excellent opportunity for outreach and general education. They also provide a means of encouraging students with extremely diverse backgrounds to take up astronomy research.